

under transplanted culture. Straw yield of Sasyashree was higher than that of Vikash in direct seeded culture, but they performed equally well when they were transplanted.

Neither culture type nor variety significantly influenced total N uptake in rice, although their interaction effect was significant. N uptake in Vikash was significantly more under transplanted condition than that of IET7959, but in direct seeded culture, the opposite was true. Vikash and IET9978 can be used for direct seeding. The two varieties also removed significantly less N when direct seeded than when they were transplanted (see table). ■

Yields and N uptake of six rice varieties under two cultures in a submerged Ustorthent. Ramachandrapuram, AP, India, 1990 WS.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw yield (t/ha)			Total N uptake (kg/ha)		
	DS ^a	TP ^b	Mean	DS	TP	Mean	DS	TP	Mean
Rasi	4.6	4.1	4.4	4.2	3.3	3.7	89.8	85.6	87.7
Sasyashree	4.0	3.5	3.7	4.8	4.5	4.7	86.2	82.4	84.3
Vikash	4.4	4.4	4.4	3.9	4.4	4.1	78.4	89.9	84.1
IET7959	4.6	4.2	4.4	3.7	3.4	3.6	88.8	81.5	85.1
IET9219	4.9	4.3	4.6	4.2	3.4	3.8	85.6	81.7	83.7
IET9978	4.4	4.4	4.4	3.8	3.8	3.8	79.4	92.3	85.8
Mean	4.5	4.2		4.1	3.8		84.7	85.6	
LSD (0.05)									
Culture (C)		ns ^c			ns			ns	
Variety (V)		0.34			0.44			ns	
C × V		ns							
C at same V					0.72			10.0	
V at same C					0.62			8.0	

^aDS = direct seeded. ^bTP = transplanted. ^cns = not significant.

Integrated pest management—diseases

Occurrence of rice grain rot disease in Vietnam

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Rice grain rot disease has caused damage in Japan, Taiwan, Philippines, and Latin America. The disease causal organism is bacterium *Pseudomonas glumae*.

Symptoms are discolored grain, husk, and endosperm. Grain is unfilled in severely infected plants.

The disease was first recorded in Vietnam in 1991 early summer rice season in the central provinces and in the summer rice season in the Red River Delta provinces. PPRI studied the disease etiology and its distribution. About 100,000 ha were infected in 1992 early summer and summer seasons. Five provinces (Ha Tay, Thai Binh, Nam Ha, Thanh Hoa, and Khanh Hoa) are reported to be disease hot spots, with crop losses of up to 75%.

To confirm the causal agent of the disease, infected grains were collected. Two botanic parasitic bacteria were isolated and identified in the laboratory. One had a yellow colony and the other, a creamy white colony. Seedborne fungi *Cercospora*, *Helminthosporium*, and *Curvularia* were also isolated.

Variety CR203, which is widely grown in the Red River Delta was artificially inoculated at the heading stage. Only the bacterium with the creamy white colony at 10⁸ cfu/ml concentration produced symptoms similar to the disease observed in the field; it was designated as isolate no. 18.

We used the method of Matsuda et al to detect *P. glumae* using a CaC₂O₄ crystal. We cultured isolate no. 18 in a potato-peptone-glucose-agar (PPGA) mixed medium and with 0.1% CaCl₂ at 38 °C. The color of the PPGA turned a pale greenish yellow, and the CaC₂O₄ crystal on the colony was observed under the microscope. *P. glumae* was identified as the causal organism. ■

Treating rice seeds with fungicides and antagonists to control seedborne diseases

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Rice blast (Bl), caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav., and brown leaf spot, caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan, are seedborne diseases that cause appreciable yield loss. We treated rice seeds with some fungicides and antagonists to assess effects on seed viability, seedling vigor, and inhibition of seedborne pathogens.

We conducted standard blotter assays using seeds of rice cultivar ADT36. *P. oryzae* infected 27.0% of the seeds and *H. oryzae*, 35.4%. Seeds were treated with fungicides and antagonists (see table), shade-dried, and stored for 5 mo. Seed viability and seedling vigor were

assessed monthly for 6 mo by roll towel method. Inhibition zone assay was used to determine inhibition of pathogens.

In the roll towel method, 10-d-old normal seedlings were selected randomly and root length, shoot length, and dry weights were measured.

Vigor index (VI) was calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{VI} &= \text{Germination \%} \times \text{root length} \\ &\quad (\text{mean of 10 seedlings, in cm}) \\ &= \text{Germination \%} \times \text{shoot length} \\ &\quad (\text{mean of 10 seedlings, in cm}) \\ &= \text{Germination \%} \times \text{dry weight} \\ &\quad (\text{mean of 10 seedlings, in mg}). \end{aligned}$$

In the inhibition zone assay, the spore suspension (10⁶ spores/ml) of the test pathogen (*P. oryzae* or *H. oryzae*) was mixed with molten potato dextrose agar medium and poured in petri plates. A treated seed was placed at the center of the medium. The diameter of the